

Research article

Terms for ‘elder brother’ and ‘elder sister’ in Kra-DaiHIRANO, Ayaka
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Abstract: In this paper, I aim to analyze terms that refer to elder brothers and elder sisters in Kra-Dai languages geolinguistically. There are two types of elder-sibling term systems in Kra-Dai languages: the ‘elder sibling’ type and the ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type. The ‘elder sibling’ distinctions are found around Guiyang in China and Southeast Asia. The most widespread form for ‘elder sibling’ is derived from Proto-Tai *bi^{B2}. The ‘elder brother/elder sister’ distinctions are found mainly in southern China and Hainan Island. All distinctions on Hainan Island are of the ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type. Although ‘elder sibling’ distinctions are more widely distributed than ‘elder brother/elder sister’ ones, words that mean ‘elder sibling’ have fewer variations. Some languages, in particular Central Tai branch languages, use both systems together. The most widespread forms for ‘elder brother’ and ‘elder sister’ might be derived from the Chinese 哥 (ge) ‘elder brother’ and 姊 (zi) ‘elder sister’, respectively. Kra-Dai has many elements borrowed from Chinese for elder siblings. Not only 哥 (ge) and 姊 (zi) have been borrowed; elements similar to 阿 (a), which is a prefix for elder people in Chinese, are also found in some languages. Although Chinese has a strong influence on elder-sibling terms in Kra-Dai languages, Hlai languages have fewer Chinese-derived elements than others. For this reason, the forms found in Hlai languages might be closer to the ancient form.

Keywords: Kra-Dai; sibling terms; loan words**1. Introduction**

This paper presents a geolinguistic analysis of words referring to elder siblings, such as ‘elder brother’ and ‘elder sister’, in Kra-Dai languages. In some Kra-Dai languages, there is no distinction between ‘elder brother’ and ‘elder sister’, and there is a word for ‘elder sibling’. On the other hand, other Kra-Dai languages have separate words for ‘elder brother’ and ‘elder sister’. In this paper, I first create linguistic maps of the distribution of the elder sibling term system. After looking at the distribution of systems according to whether or not there is a gender distinction, I examine the distribution of each form of ‘elder sibling’, ‘elder brother’, and ‘elder sister’ found in Kra-Dai languages.

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2. System of Elder Sibling Terms

Figure 1 shows the distribution of the ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type languages and the ‘elder sibling’ type languages. The ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type languages have gender-differentiated words for ‘elder brother’ and ‘elder sister’, whereas the ‘elder sibling’ type languages do not distinguish between the two genders. As shown in Figure 1, the geographical distribution of the ‘elder sibling’ type is wider in Southeast Asia and around Guiyang Province, China. The ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type is more common in southern China and Hainan Island.

Fig. 1 Distribution of the elder sibling term system in Kra-Dai languages

Each language subclass in the distribution illustrated in Figure 1 shows a different situation. As shown in Figure 2, many languages in the Southwestern Tai languages have a system that does not distinguish elder siblings by gender, while some languages

distributed in China distinguish elder siblings by gender. Some languages use the systems of ‘elder sibling’ and ‘elder brother/elder sister’ together.

Fig. 2 Distribution of the elder sibling term system in Southwestern Tai languages

Central Tai languages also have ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type languages, which are distributed in China, as shown in Figure 3. However, the boundary between the ‘elder brother/elder sister’ and ‘elder sibling’ types is more ambiguous than in the Southwest Tai languages, and some languages use the two systems together.

Fig. 3 Distribution of the elder sibling term system in Central Tai languages

In Northern Tai languages, the distribution area of the ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type and the ‘elder sibling’ type is divided. In Bouyei languages, the ‘elder sibling’ type is dominant, while in the northern Zhuang dialects, the ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type is dominant, resulting in the distribution shown in Figure 4. In some northern Zhuang dialects, the ‘elder brother/elder sister’ type system and the ‘elder sibling’ type system are used together.

Fig. 4 Distribution of the elder sibling term system in Northern Tai languages

In Kam-Sui and Kra languages, the 'elder brother/elder sister' type predominates, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 Distribution of the elder sibling term system in Kam-Sui and Kra languages

Hlai and Ong Be languages spoken on Hainan Island are all of the 'elder brother/elder sister' type system, as shown in Figure 6, as far as I was able to ascertain at this time.

Fig. 6 Distribution of the elder sibling term system in Hlai and Ong Be languages

In some languages, it is reported that the meaning corresponding to ‘elder brother’ or ‘elder sister’ can be expressed by modifying the ‘elder sibling’ element with elements expressing gender. Figure 8 shows the distribution of modifiers in the languages of the ‘elder sibling’ type that can be used to express ‘male elder sibling’. The most widespread type is the CAAI type.

Fig. 8 Distribution of male modifiers for ‘elder sibling’

The distribution of modifiers used to express ‘female elder sibling’ is shown in Figure 9. Although the number of languages I was able to examine is limited, compared to the distribution of modifiers for ‘male’ shown in Figure 8, none of the forms can be observed as widely as the CAAI form for ‘male’.

Fig. 9 Distribution of female modifiers for ‘elder sibling’

4. ‘Elder Brother’

As shown in Figure 10, the most widespread form is similar to *ko*. This KO type is thought to be a borrowing of the Chinese word 哥 (*ge*) ‘elder brother’. The TA type is similar to one of the forms of ‘elder sibling’ observed in section 3, and the PI/PHI type is the most widespread form of ‘elder sibling’ seen in section 3, but it is used in the sense of ‘elder brother’ in some languages. The PI/PHI type form as ‘elder brother’ is sometimes used with the KO type form in one language. The (W)ENG/WING type is predominant in the Hainan Island Hlai languages.

Fig. 10 Distribution of ‘elder brother’

A form prefixed with a kind of prefix similar to the Chinese 阿 (a) is found at 10 sites. As Figure 11 shows, none are found on Hainan Island; all are found on the mainland. 阿 (a) in Chinese is a prefix for elder people. Thus, it may be due to language contact with Chinese.

Fig. 11 Distribution of the ‘A+elder brother’ form

5. ‘Elder Sister’

As shown in Figure 12, the SE/CHE type is the most widespread. The SE/CHE type may be a borrowing from 姊 (zi) since 姊 (zi) is pronounced like *tse* in the Chaozhou dialect of Chinese¹. On Hainan Island, the TA and PI type are also observed as forms of ‘elder sister’. The EI/AU and KHAU types are predominant on Hainan Island.

¹ In southern Vietnamese dialects belonging to the Austro-Asiatic language family, ‘elder sister’ is *ché*, similar to the SE/CHE type of Kra-Dai; Lê Ngọc Trữ (1993) suggests that it may be a loan word from Chaozhou or Cantonese dialects.

Fig. 12 Distribution of 'elder sister'

Like 'elder brother' in section 4, 'elder sister' is often observed in a form with an attached prefix similar to the Chinese 阿 (a), which is found at 7 sites. Figure 13 shows its distribution; like the A+ 'elder brother' form, it is not observed on Hainan Island.

Fig. 13 Distribution of the 'A+elder sister' form

6. Conclusion

There are two systems in Kra-Dai; the 'elder sibling' system and the 'elder brother/elder sister' system. Some languages use both of these systems together. The most widespread forms of 'elder brother' and 'elder sister' appear to be loan words from Chinese, and the influence of Chinese can be seen strongly in these forms.

However, in the languages of Hainan Island, especially in the Hlai languages, the use of Chinese-derived forms is limited. In other words, the forms found in the Hlai languages may be closer to the original Kra-Dai lexical form.

Data sources

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